

Table 1. Effect of buprofezin on 3d-instar BPH, GLH, and WBPH nymphs using Potter's spray tower and foliar spray at 0.075% concentration.^a

Treatment	Potter's spray						Foliar spray					
	3 DAT			5 DAT			3 DAT			5 DAT		
	BPH	GLH	WBPH	BPH	GLH	WBPH	BPH	GLH	WBPH	BPH	GLH	WBPH
Buprofezin	100 a	99a	100a	100a	99a	100a	100a	98a	99a	100a	98a	100a
Control	5 b	8 b	1 b	9 b	10 b	10 b	2 b	0 b	6 b	6 b	2 b	12 b

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. DAT = days after treatment.

Table 2. Effect of buprofezin rates on BPH field populations.

Treatment	Means of BPH count after insecticide application ^a									
	1st application			2d application			3d application			
	2 DBFA ^b	5 DAT	10 DAT	15 DAT	5 DAT	10 DAT	15 DAT	5 DAT	10 DAT	15 DAT
Buprofezin										
0.125 kg ai/ha	30.69	11.02 a	11.51 a	10.48 ab	5.80 c	11.66 ab	5.52 d	3.32 b	2.46 b	2.69 bc
0.250 kg ai/ha	26.19	10.36 a	11.21 a	9.49 b	5.15 c	11.94 ab	6.09 c	3.31 b	2.68 b	2.34 c
0.500 kg ai/ha	27.62	10.09 a	11.60 a	10.20 ab	5.00 c	11.76 ab	6.29 c	3.47 b	2.80 b	2.49 bc
BPMC										
0.75 kg ai/ha	25.55	10.99 a	12.09 a	12.06 a	6.50 b	7.86 b	7.09 b	3.28 b	3.05 b	4.72 b
Control	29.40	11.60 a	12.85 a	11.35 ab	16.41 a	18.50 a	15.99 a	13.70 a	13.20 a	14.71 a

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bDBFA = days before first application, DAT = days after treatment.

Light trap catches of green leafhoppers by time of day

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Nephotettix spp. are the predominant species of rice leafhoppers and plant-hoppers in Eastern Uttar Pradesh. Seasonal population fluctuations and hopper species dominance have been recorded regularly since 1976 using light traps installed on the research farm. Traps operate from 1800 to 0600 hours daily. Light trap catches indicate the necessary level of green leafhopper control. We conducted a study to determine the best time of day to trap leafhoppers. Three Mitsuo Yoshimuki light traps with double coiled 210–240 volt tungsten mercury vapor filaments and a 160-watt electric bulb were installed 200 m apart and operated for 3 successive nights at weekly intervals. Insect numbers in each catch were recorded hourly from 1900 to 0600.

Most green leafhoppers were trapped between 1900 to 2100 hours. Catches

Catches of rice green leafhopper by hour of day.

Hour	Catch at 3 trapping dates ^a (198 1)			Mean catch	% catch
	19 Oct	26 Oct	2 Nov		
1800–1900	97	93	64	84.73	14
1900–2000	146	115	71	110.82	19
2000–2100	130	112	67	103.03	17
2100–2200	104	88	56	82.60	14
2200–2300	96	74	42	70.68	12
2300–2400	67	50	30	48.72	8
2400–0100	47	35	20	33.84	6
0100–0200	39	23	13	24.63	4
0200–0300	22	16	7	15.45	3
0300–0400	11	10	6	9.03	1
0400–0500	10	7	4	7.20	1
0500–0600	7	5	3	5.11	1
Total	776.21	630.17	381.12		
CD at 5% level	17.172	16.757	18.354		
CD at 1% level	23.341	12.777	24.948		

^aData were converted to square root ($\sqrt{n+0.5}$), then rounded.

between 1800 to 1900, and 2100 and 2200 were also high. After 2200, catches decreased toward morning. Of total leafhoppers trapped, 39% were caught between 1900 and 2100 hours, and 64% during the first 4 hours (see table). These data indicate light traps can be used most efficiently between 1900 and 2100 hours.

Light trap catches of rice gall midge

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From Jul 1981 to Mar 1982, a bamboo light trap with a 40-watt bulb was oper-

ated at the ACRI experimental farm, Madurai, to determine population fluctuations and peak emergence of rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason). The data will help scientists predict pest occurrence and insecticide applications.

The earliest gall midge capture was in the second week of Aug. Populations gradually increased until mid-Oct, then declined (see figure). Peak occurrence coincided with the maximum tillering phase of the rice crop. □

Adult midges collected in a bamboo light-trap with a 40-watt bulb, Madurai, India, 1981-82.

Insecticide toxicity to natural brown planthopper enemies

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We investigated contact toxicity of some foliar insecticides on brown planthopper predators: the mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* Reuter and spiders, *Lycosa* sp., that inhabit the rice ecosystem

Two 10-day-old TN1 seedlings were planted in clay pots. Plants were sprayed with insecticides 20 days after planting; 24 h later 10 adult mirid bugs (5 males and 5 females) were released per pot and confined in mylar cages. To prevent the predators from starving, three to four BPH nymphs were released in each pot.

Twenty spiderlings were forced to crawl over a chemical solution film in a

Toxicity of insecticides to brown planthopper predators.^a

Insecticide	Corrected mortality ^b (%)	
	<i>C. lividipennis</i>	<i>Lycosa</i> sp.
Decamethrin 0.002%	100 a	98 a
Methyl parathion 0.04%	100 a	98 a
Cypermethrin 0.002%	93 a	93 a
Fenvalerate 0.002%	93 a	92 a
Quinalphos 0.04%	93 a	92 a
Phosalone 0.04%	93 a	92 a
Permethrin 0.002%	92 a	90 a
Fenthion 0.04%	85 ab	90 a
Methamidophos 0.04%	76 b	87 ab
Phosphamidon 0.04%	76 b	79 b
FMC35001 0.04%	76 b	74 b

^a Mean of 3 replications. ^b Analysis based on arcsin/percentage values. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

large petri dish for 2 min then immediately transferred to glass tubes which were covered with muslin. Predator mortality was recorded 24 h after treatment.

Decamethrin and methyl parathion caused 100% *C. lividipennis* mortality,

closely followed by cypermethrin, fenvalerate, quinalphos, phosalone, and permethrin (see table). All insecticides tested were highly toxic to spiderlings. Mortality ranged from 74% (FMC35001) to 98% (decamethrin and methyl parathion). □

Pest management and control WEEDS

Sawdust-mulching for controlling weeds in transplanted summer rice

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Weeds are a major constraint to successful summer rice cultivation in Assam. Sawdust mulch 0, 2, and 4 cm thick was tested for weed control on Pusa 33, Mairang, and Ngoba in a split-plot design with 4 replications. On 25 Apr, 25-day-old seedlings were transplanted in 20 × 15 cm

Table 1. Fresh weight of weeds per 1.8 m² in rice fields with different sawdust mulching.

Variety	Fresh wt (g) of weeds			Mean ^a
	0	2-cm mulch	4-cm mulch	
Pusa 33	960	700	720	793.3 b
Mairang	2790	1466	853	1703.0 a
Ngoba	1100	1016	866	944.0 b
Mean ^a	1616.7 a	1060.7 b	873.0 c	

^a Any two means followed by different letters are significantly different at 5% level of probability.

spacing on 9-m² plots. At land preparation, 80 kg N, 21.5 kg P, and 33 kg K/ha were applied. Weed samples were col-

lected from 1.8-m² strips from each plot. Mulching significantly suppressed weed growth (Table 1). Weed weights